

Annealing in Irradiated Strontium Nitrate

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The isothermal annealing in γ -irradiated strontium nitrate has been studied at different temperatures in the range 180-250°. The annealing data have been analysed on the basis of conventional chemical kinetics and also on the basis of models developed by Fletcher and Brown, and by Waite. It is found that the annealing process can be represented by the combination of one rapid first order and one slow second order reaction, each with a different energy of activation. In the annealing process, the oxygen fragment combines with the nitrite to form the original nitrate, the recombination taking place at normal lattice sites.

THE chemical damage induced in crystalline nitrates by irradiation recovers when the irradiated crystals are heated¹. The kinetics as well as the role of lattice defects on the kinetics of isothermal recovery of irradiation damage has been investigated in some detail only in the case of lead nitrate¹⁻⁴. The annealing of radiolytic damage in sodium and rubidium nitrates has been studied by Chandunni and Nair⁵ and it has been observed that the annealing in these systems is quite different from that of lead nitrate. It was of interest therefore to investigate the annealing of radiolytic damage in alkaline earth nitrates. Mohanty and Upadhyay⁶ have reported annealing in irradiated barium nitrate in the temperature range 200-275°. This paper reports annealing of chemical radiation damage in strontium nitrate.

Materials and Method

Analytical reagent grade strontium nitrate (BDH) was used. The material was seived to obtain crystals in the 85-100 mesh range and it was dried over phosphorus pentoxide.

Samples sealed *in vacuo* (3×10^{-3} m.m. Hg) in glass ampoules were irradiated with ⁶⁰Co γ -rays to a dose of 52 Mrad at the dose rate of 0.19 Mrad hr⁻¹. The irradiated crystals were preserved over phosphorus pentoxide before examination or thermal treatment.

Isothermal annealing runs were made in air in a thermostatic electric hot air oven maintained to within $\pm 0.5^\circ$ of the desired temperature.

The damage nitrite was estimated spectrophotometrically with a PYE UNICAM SP 1800 Spectrophotometer by the Shinn⁷ method as modified by Kershaw and Chamberlin⁸. Repetitive determinations showed less than 1 per cent variation.

Results and Discussion

The colouration induced by irradiation and the bleaching upon thermal annealing of the irradiated crystals were similar to those reported earlier¹. The initial damage produced by 52 Mrad of ⁶⁰Co γ -rays in different samples of strontium nitrate varied between 790-830 p.p.m. of nitrite.

The thermal annealing of the damage was investigated at various temperatures in the range 180-250°. The results are recorded in Fig. 1 in which the fraction of the nitrite annealed,

$$\varphi = \{[\text{NO}_2^-]_0 - [\text{NO}_2^-]_t\} / [\text{NO}_2^-]_0 \quad \dots (1)$$

where $[\text{NO}_2^-]_0$ is the initial nitrite content of the irradiated crystals and $[\text{NO}_2^-]_t$, the nitrite content at heating time t in hours, is plotted against the time of heating. The magnitude of annealing in strontium nitrate is greater than that observed in barium nitrate⁶.

Fig. 1. Annealing in γ -irradiated strontium nitrate

From a plot of $1/[\text{NO}_2^-]$ against t (Fig. 2) it is seen that, except for early times when the reaction

Fig. 2. The second order plot for annealing in γ -irradiated strontium nitrate

is too much rapid, the annealing at a given temperature is represented by second order kinetics. The reacting species, viz. nitrite ions and oxygen fragments, are present in equal concentration, and therefore, the second order rate expression is

$$k_{II} = \frac{1[\text{NO}_2^-]_1 - [\text{NO}_2^-]_2}{(t_2 - t_1)[\text{NO}_2^-]_1[\text{NO}_2^-]_2} \quad (2)$$

where $[\text{NO}_2^-]_1$ and $[\text{NO}_2^-]_2$ are the values of the nitrite concentration at times t_1 and t_2 respectively. The values of the second order velocity constants k_{II} for different temperatures calculated from Equation (2) in the range of linearity of the $1/[\text{NO}_2^-]$ versus t plots are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—TEMPERATURE VARIATION OF FIRST AND SECOND ORDER VELOCITY CONSTANTS IN ANNEALING IN STRONTIUM NITRATE

Temp. °C	k_I hr ⁻¹	k_{II} p.p.m. ⁻¹ .hr ⁻¹
180	0.699	0.0231
190	0.833	0.0308
200	1.044	0.0451
210	1.259	0.0679
220	1.535	0.0980
230	1.820	0.1128
240	2.188	0.1958
250	2.630	0.1750

The nature of departure from second order behaviour over the initial stages of heating indicates

the simultaneous occurrence of another reaction which is faster and is virtually complete in the first few hours of heating after which the kinetics is entirely of the second order. Subtraction of the concentration $[\text{NO}_2^-]_{II}$ of the nitrite which recombines bimolecularly from the experimental values gives the concentration of the nitrite $[\text{NO}_2^-]_I$ which anneals according to the other process :

$$[\text{NO}_2^-] = [\text{NO}_2^-]_I + [\text{NO}_2^-]_{II} \quad \dots (3)$$

Fig. 3 shows that $\log [\text{NO}_2^-]_I$ is linearly related

Fig. 3. The first order contribution to annealing in γ -irradiated strontium nitrate

to time t , as is characteristic of a first order reaction :

$$[\text{NO}_2^-]_{I,t} = [\text{NO}_2^-]_{I,0} \exp(-k_1 t) \quad \dots (4)$$

The first order velocity constants k_1 are given in Table 1. Thus, it is evident that the annealing is accurately represented by the combination of one rapid first order reaction which goes to completion within a few hours after the commencement of heating, and a slow second order process.

The mean values of the proportions of the original nitrite which recombine by the first and the second order mechanisms are 8 and 92 per cent respectively. As may be expected these values are independent of temperature. From the temperature dependence of the first and second order velocity constants (Fig. 4), the energy of activation is calculated as 8.9 and 15.0 kcal mole⁻¹ respectively.

The fact that annealing can be represented by the combination of two processes indicates that irradiation generates two different damage species^{1,6,9};

Fig. 4. Energetics of various kinetic processes

(i) Nitrite ion-oxygen atom pairs in such close proximity as to be within each others' perturbing influence. The oxygen atom is situated at the interstitial position adjacent to the lattice site of the nitrite ion from the same event. It is assumed that the damage pairs are far removed from, and do not interact with one another. Such a pair falls apart on dissolution with the consequent formation of nitrite ion in solution, and the evolution of oxygen. On acquisition of the appropriate activation energy, the oxygen atom jumps back to the original lattice position and interacts there with the nitrite ion. This motion is favoured in preference to migration away from the nitrite ion because the activation energy involved is smaller than that required for the latter process. These correlated nitrite ion-oxygen atom pairs decay according to the first order law.

(ii) The second species consists of nitrite ions and oxygen fragments which have been completely liberated from each other. The oxygen fragments involved are those which had diffused out from the damage site during irradiation, and had got trapped at vacant lattice sites. These fragments, or related species, are released on heating, migrate through the crystal, and undergo random recombination with the nitrite ions by second order kinetics.

The present data have also been analysed in terms of models proposed for the recovery of interstitial-vacancy damage produced in solids by bombardment¹⁰. The model due to Waite^{11, 12} considers recovery as a diffusion limited reaction. The resulting expression for the kinetics of recovery is very complex, but for small initial defect concentration and early times

$$\varphi = K(Dt)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (5)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient and K , a quantity independent of temperature. The change of the initial $\varphi/t^{\frac{1}{2}}$ with temperature gives the temperature dependence of D which is of the form

$$D = D_0 \exp(-E/kT) \quad \dots (6)$$

Our data are presented in Fig. 5 as a graph of φ against $t^{\frac{1}{2}}$. It is seen that the curves are linear for early times in agreement with the theory. The activation energy calculated from the temperature dependence of $\varphi/t^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Fig. 4) is 18.5 k cal mole⁻¹. Fig. 6 shows that annealing data taken at different temperatures can be represented as a unique function of $(Dt)^{\frac{1}{2}} = [D_0 \exp(-E/kT) t]^{\frac{1}{2}}$. It is evident that the initial part of this universal curve is linear.

In the model due to Fletcher and Brown¹³⁻¹⁶ annealing is considered to occur in three stages corresponding to three distinct mechanisms of recombination, viz. close pair, liberation, and second order. Annealing in all the stages is a function of t/τ , where τ is the average jump time given by the relation

$$\tau = 1/\nu \quad (7)$$

Fig. 5. Annealing as a function of square root of heating time

Fig. 6. Waite composite annealing curve

where ν is the vibration frequency that depends on temperature in the usual way,

$$\nu = \nu_0 \exp(-E/kT) \quad \dots (8)$$

Thus, it is possible to combine the data of a number of annealing curves at different temperatures simply by adjusting the time scale by a constant factor for each isothermal annealing curve. This time scale adjustment factor is the ratio of the time taken for a certain fraction to anneal at the reference temperature to that at the given temperature¹⁵. Our data are plotted in Fig. 7 against the equivalent time t'

Fig. 7. Fletcher-Brown composite annealing curve

at a reference temperature 220° (493°K). t' is obtained by multiplying the time of annealing at a given temperature by the time scale adjustment

factor¹⁵. The data are adequately superimposed and fit the following combination of a first order and a second order process shown by the continuous curve in the figure :

$$\phi = 0.079[1 - \exp(-t'/1.362)] + 0.921[1/(1+909/t')] \quad (9)$$

The logarithm of the relative jump time $\tau_{(493^\circ K)}/\tau_{(T)}$ is a linear function of $1/T$ (Fig. 4) and the activation energy is 18.3 kcal mole⁻¹. It is of interest that both the Waite and the Fletcher-Brown treatments give values for the energy of activation for migration which are very nearly the same.

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